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Interseasonal transfer learning for crop mapping using Sentinel-1 data

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ABSTRACT

Crop maps are highly desired information in modern agriculture as they enable possessors to manage their business in the most optimal way. Usually in remote sensing, crop mapping is performed using satellite images and within-season ground truth samples that are collected in extensive survey campaigns every year, neglecting information and knowledge that past seasons' classification models provided. This paper assessed different temporal transferring approaches, including transfer learning, together with traditional crop mapping approach to provide an exhaustive comparison. Transferring approaches differed in portion of knowledge utilized from a historical model and that coming from a target season dataset. Three distinct algorithms, Random Forest, Convolutional Neural Network and Transformer, were employed and evaluated using highly dense time series of Sentinel-1 data. Source and target domain were respectively represented by two sets, 2017–2020 and 2021 season data, and 9 different crop types were classified. Results showcased that transferring a model has a great potential in crop mapping when little to no ground truth data is available for the target season. However, traditional approach catches up rather quickly and even surpasses transfer learning approach in terms of performance after a certain portion of target domain data is collected. Without target season ground truth data, model transferring can yield modest crop mapping performance of 78% for F1 score, between 84% and 86% F1 score with transfer learning employed in conjunction with limited target season ground truth (i.e. between 120 and 720 parcels), and 88% F1 score at best with traditional approach (ca. 720 parcels). Even though a good discriminatory is found between different crop types, there is still a room for improvement regarding the least represented classes in the dataset. The study significantly contributes to the area of agricultural monitoring and management by demonstrating the effectiveness of transfer learning while lessening the necessity for extensive and labor-intensive data collection, thereby fostering cost and time efficiency. Utilizing Sentinel-1 data, it provides a practical and efficient solution for agricultural analysis worldwide regardless of cloudiness.

1. Introduction

Access to food, food security, and food production have been key factors driving human progress since ancient times, often resulting in both conflict and peace negotiations. The present global circumstances have elevated food-related concerns to an unprecedented level. In order to ensure sufficient and qualitative food supplies, special attention needs to be given to crop production, and thus to timely and accurate crop monitoring. Accurate agricultural maps (crop maps, land use maps) are essential in supporting decision makers to create optimal policies that ensure food security (Blickensdörfer et al., 2022). Nowadays, prerequisites for generating this type of information are met, having in mind the increasing number of publicly available satellite

imagery together with accompanying advances in machine learning (ML) and its subfield deep learning (DL) (Turkoglu et al., 2021).

Different actions have been made in recent years that promote the use of Earth observation (EO) data as means to detect/control presence of cultivars declared by farmers or even illegal crops (Arias et al., 2020; Rußwurm et al., 2019). In some European countries it is mandatory for farmers to declare what type of cultivar they will produce and sometimes it is required to report it in order to receive financial support within the scope of Common Agricultural Policy (Arias et al., 2020) and national subsidy programmes. Occasionally this data is open to the public. This results in creation of datasets such as EuroCrops (Schneider et al., 2021), ZueriCrop (Turkoglu et al., 2021), BreizhCrops (Rußwurm et al., 2019) and others, that include over hundreds of thousands of

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labeled parcels suitable for high-quality training of machine learning models. However, some countries, especially the European Union candidate states, lack the mandatory formal system of farmer's cultivar declaration which is why it is hard to acquire any large ground truth dataset for these regions. For this reason, production potential of these regions often remains unexplored despite favorable agro-ecological conditions. What is more, any continental-scale classification model for Europe continues to self-integrate at least partial bias towards better represented regions in the reference dataset. This paper represents an attempt to bring one of the weakly represented agricultural regions in literature into focus, Vojvodina (northernmost part of Serbia), and explore and promote actionable use of artificial intelligence (AI) for crop mapping that can grapple with the insufficient labeled data.

Traditional crop mapping using satellite imagery is based on optical or (and) radar images, and reference data, i.e., ground truth for the season that is collected by performing field campaigns and labeling at the beginning of the season. This is found to be rather labor-intensive and also an expensive way of ground truth data collection (Turkoglu et al., 2021; Arias et al., 2020) but unfortunately it is very often the only possible way to do it.

Collection of a detailed large-scale database of ground truth data would require involvement of higher-level instances of public authorities who would have to establish a set of regulations on how and where data is collected and stored, who can use it, and for what purpose. This is practiced in some developed countries as mentioned, but even then, a question on the completeness and reliability of the data remains. With the aim to enlarge or replace ground truth datasets obtained through field based sampling strategies, some forms of algorithmical generation of pseudo ground truth have already been tested for crop mapping (Lin et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). Furthermore, there were also conscious attempts to use ML-generated datasets, such as Crop Land Datalayer, as ground truth for crop mapping (Hao et al., 2020; Yuan and Lin, 2020; Cai et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021) even though this data contains apparent inherited errors of the initial processing pipeline. Despite the doubts, benefits over detriments are evident as massive collections of ground truth data provide a valuable and indispensable resource for many classification tasks. Numerous papers explored crop mapping problem using SAR in the presence of plethora of ground truth data; whether through the extraction of temporal signature of crops, followed by the comparison of the time series of spectral response of the element of interest to it Arias et al. (2020), Whelen and Siqueira (2018) and Xu et al. (2019), or by utilizing various machine learning and deep learning techniques (Qu et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2021; Reußel et al., 2021), or in combination with optical data (Blickensdorfer et al., 2022; Orynbaikyzy et al., 2020; Tricht et al., 2018).

In order to alleviate the necessity for (yearly) ground truth data collection, an inter-annual transfer of classification models can be explored. While model transfer can be employed directly without adaptations, i.e., without any use of reference data of the target year, this paper considers as “transfer learning” (TL) an approach where previously acquired model knowledge is combined with limited target year reference data to produce a new knowledge, i.e., a new model, that potentially performs better than the pure transfer approach.

Yang et al. (2020) give a definition of transfer learning in the following way: “Given a source domain D_s and learning task T_s , a target domain D_t and learning task T_t , transfer learning aims to help improve the learning of the target predictive function $f_t(\cdot)$ for the target domain using the knowledge in D_s and T_s , where $D_s \neq D_t$ or $T_s \neq T_t$ ”.

In this experiment the ultimate goal is to classify the same crop types in different seasons so it is assumed that domains are different ($D_s \neq D_t$), rather than tasks, because seasons vary in weather conditions, farmers' practice, etc.

Transfer learning goes under various terminologies in AI and domain adaptation is one of them (Yang et al., 2020). Depending on whether some or none of the labeled data from target source are used for model adaptation, it is referred to as supervised or unsupervised

domain adaptation, or semi-supervised domain adaptation if both types of data is used Lucas et al. (2021).

Studies dealing with transferability of crop mapping models, in comparison to the traditional crop mapping using satellite imagery, are usually more of a new age, and can be divided roughly into two categories, those dealing with transferability in the temporal domain (You and Dong, 2020; Cai et al., 2018; Hu et al., 2022), and those dealing with transferability in the spatial domain (Orynbaikyzy et al., 2022; Jo et al., 2022; Yuan and Lin, 2020). Combination of the two, i.e., spatio-temporal transferability as a simultaneous method is in particular a complex task and thus seldomly seen in the literature (Hao et al., 2020; Gilcher and Udelhoven, 2021). Very often model transfers seen in literature fit to the category of simple or naive transfer, i.e., transfer without adaptations, whereas transfer learning approaches, i.e., transfer with adaptations, recently started getting more and more attention. Those of the latter group sometimes try to transfer the knowledge from computer vision tasks to crop mapping by fine-tuning parameters of previously trained models (Nowakowski et al., 2021; Gadiraju and Vatsavai, 2020).

1.1. Research premise

The premise of this research arise from findings given in Hu et al. (2022), which states that ground truth data does not need to be gathered every year and that interannual transfer of the trained models can be used for predicting (future) and retracing (historical) crop type maps. While Hu et al. (2022) performed pure transfer of model, this paper aims to investigate benefits of using small amounts of ground truth of the target year (in combination with very dense time series of SAR data) and check if (at all) and by what rate (how much) accuracy can benefit from introducing certain portions of this data.

Due to susceptibility to weather conditions, notably cloud cover, optical data could not provide as dense time series as SAR data can (Orynbaikyzy et al., 2022). Thus, transferring models based on optical data could be rather challenging, having in mind lots of potential constraints (cloudiness of the area, number of valid images during the season, adequate matching day-of-year of the valid images in source and target domain, etc.), which does not apply for SAR. There are attempts to densify optical time series, but they all require additional processing, whether using interpolation or some other more advanced machine learning methods, that bring in additional uncertainty. Quantifying this induced uncertainty is by itself a complex task, and thus it is seldom (or hardly ever) seen in crop mapping research in literature. In that sense, SAR based approaches are more robust and suitable for wider application. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to utilize temporal transfer learning in combination with densely sampled radar time series for multi-class crop mapping, making our research unique in this aspect.

The research starts off by creating a dense time series of SAR data, followed by building different crop classification models and approaches. Objective is to assess the potential of temporal transfer learning in the northern Serbian province of Vojvodina. By incorporating data from multiple seasons in the experiment, we tend to create robust models that can learn invariant features and generalize well, thus successfully handle year-to-year variations. Given that the phenological development and growing patterns of a crop are the same or quite similar between different regions (Hao et al., 2020), similarities of a crop among seasons of the same region is even more apparent which enables us to base hypothesis upon. Research questions addressed in this paper are:

1. Is it possible to transfer the knowledge of the crop classification model in temporal domain within a particular region?
2. How do different portions of ground truth data of the target year added to the training set affect classification results?
3. What are advantages and disadvantages of transfer learning compared to standard crop mapping procedure?

Fig. 1. Example of fragmented agricultural land in Vojvodina (Google Maps, 2022).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Study area and datasets (including preprocessing) are described in detail in Section 2, while methodology is presented in Section 3. Results are reported in Sections 4 and 5 discusses outcomes of the study. Finally, Section 6 provides conclusions and outlook for future work.

2. Data and study area

2.1. Study area

This paper covers the territory of Autonomous Province of Vojvodina. It lies in the North of the Republic of Serbia and represents the south-eastern part of the Pannonian Basin (Hrnjak et al., 2014). Vojvodina covers ca. 21,500 km² large region characterized with flatness and predominantly occupied by agriculture (Lugonja et al., 2019). According to a 2018 report, nearly 80% of the territory was used for agricultural production, i.e., 15,743 km² (RZS Srbije, 2019). The agricultural output of the province makes a significant contribution to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), accounting for 3.7% of the total in 2021 (RZS Srbije, 2023).

Hrnjak et al. (2014), describe Vojvodina's climate as moderate continental, with cold winters and hot and humid summers with huge range of extreme temperatures and nonequal distribution of rainfall per months. These extremes are even more evident nowadays, which is why the United Nations report (Jachia and Milovanović, 2022) lists Serbian agriculture as vulnerable to climate change related droughts and floods. Hence, continuous and reliable monitoring of agricultural production is of high importance for the region.

Family farms, which comprise over 99% of all farms in Serbia, have an average size of 5 hectares (RZS Srbije, 2019). Consequently, this results in a highly fragmented agricultural area throughout the country and Vojvodina is equally affected (Fig. 1). However, small size fields as such should not present a problem for pixel-based classification (Crnojević et al., 2014).

2.2. Ground truth data

This research spans over 5 agricultural seasons, from 2017 to 2021. In each season, ground truth data was collected during field campaigns. Prior to field campaigns for ground truth data collection, regions of interest were defined that were characterized with the presence of

Table 1
Number of points collected per season.

Year	Number of labeled parcels	Number of samples
2017	1183	57 330
2018	2233	108 869
2019	1753	86 143
2020	2271	112 037
2021	2399	119 294

medium and large size parcels. Due to its high resolution, Google Earth was used for this task but also because it enables to verify that these areas were “resistant” to parcel fragmentation in the past. During field campaigns, experts (in teams of two) tended to label as large parcels as possible, ensuring a sufficient number of 10 × 10 m pixels within. For this purpose, they were trying to avoid long and narrow (less than 100 m in width) parcels, preferring a layout that is both uniform and consolidated. For each parcel a label and GPS location were recorded (from within the parcel), together with any other necessary information for easier visual interpretation later on (e.g. presence of small woody features). Starting from 2019, a dedicated in-house built app was used that also records images, which were used for another independent check upon the completion of the campaign. Field campaigns were usually performed in the end of May or beginning of June. Some of the challenges faced during data collection was inaccessibility of the planned fields due to bad weather conditions (rain, mud) or natural obstacles (channel, bushes, etc.), for which alternative parcels were selected and some field trips were postponed. Upon return from field work, collected data was exported to QGIS (2022) and parcels were digitized manually by GIS experts using the Sentinel-2 imagery of 10 m resolution as the base map. Typically, the closest available satellite image to date of expedition was selected unless it was obscured by clouds in which case the following closest cloud free image was selected. Parcel borders were drawn by visually estimating the homogeneous area around the recorded GPS point that represented the same field. Practice was to always draw borders a pixel or two inside the very parcel, to make sure the effect of border pixels is avoided later in processing. Any unclear records were instantly discarded and not used further on. The number of labeled polygons per season is given in Table 1. Data of 2017–2020 seasons served as source domain, while 2021 season data served as target domain in the experiment. Spatial distribution of polygons per domain is given in Fig. 2.

As shown in Fig. 3, nine crop types were selected for this classification task, namely: corn, wheat, soybean, sunflower, sugar beet, oilseed rape, barley, clover, and orchard. Among these, the average parcel size is ca. 14 ha, but the median parcel size is ca. 4.5 ha. Variation between parcel sizes is quite large with the smallest parcel size being just 0.037 ha (corn), and the largest of about 317 ha (wheat).

In this experiment 50 randomly selected pixels within each parcel were taken as dataset samples. Due to small size of several parcels and resolution of satellite images, not every parcel was able to provide all 50 independent pixels. Yet, these parcels with fewer than 50 pixels were still taken into account. A choice of 50 pixels was selected in order to ensure efficient computation given the available resources, as well as to restrain the class imbalance from getting bigger in case more pixels were taken per parcel. Number of pixel samples given per season are presented in Table 1.

2.3. Sentinel-1

Sentinel-1 is the synthetic aperture radar satellite mission and the first satellite mission of the Copernicus programme developed by the European Space Agency which consists of two polar orbiting satellites, Sentinel-1 A and Sentinel-1B, respectively launched in April of 2014 and 2015 (Pandžić et al., 2020; Potin et al., 2016). Instruments onboard operate with the central frequency of 5.405 GHz (C-band), support

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of polygons in source and target domain.

Fig. 3. Representation of crops in the ground truth, as the share in the total number of samples.

dual polarization, and operates in four different acquisition modes, namely Stripmap, Interferometric Wide swath (IW), Extra-Wide swath and Wave mode (ESA, 2022a; Yague-Martinez et al., 2016), of which IW mode with the swath width of 250 km was used for the experiment. Data products of Sentinel-1 are available as Level-1 Single Look Complex or Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD), and the revisit time of the constellation is 6 days. As of December 23rd, 2021, due to an onboard anomaly, new Sentinel-1B data is no longer available and the end of mission for this satellite was announced (SCHUB, 2022), leaving Sentinel-1 A alone in operation with a 12-day revisit time.

Sentinel-1 IW GRD data for the experiment was acquired from Alaska Satellite Facility - ASF (ASF, 2022). ASF provides simple way to select area and desired time span, and then generates Python code which triggers data download upon run. Total of 606 images were

Fig. 4. Sentinel-1 preprocessing workflow.

downloaded that span over full five calendar years (January 1st, 2017, to December 31st, 2021) and provide information for 303 dates. All the acquisitions come from the relative orbit number 175 and they were preprocessed according to the steps described in following section.

2.4. Preprocessing of satellite imagery

SAR imagery preprocessing pipeline is depicted in Fig. 4 and was conducted using readily available *snappy* Python library (for more

Fig. 5. Methodology framework. Source domain data (historical data, i.e. seasons 2017–2020) served for hyperparameter optimization in FS (hist) approach, and for hyperparameter optimization and model training in TL and naive approaches. Target domain data (season 2021) was split into 60% for testing for all approaches, 30% for re/training, and 10% for validation purpose during hyperparameter optimization in FS (2021) approach.

details readers are referred to official SNAP development page [SNAP, 2022](#) and [STEP FORUM ESA, 2022b](#)).

It starts off by reading a pair of images covering the test area and performing *apply orbit file*, *thermal noise removal*, *border noise removal* and *calibration* to Beta0 (radar brightness). Then, the two images are merged using *slice assembly* and their *subset* to the region of interest (ROI) is extracted. This is followed by *speckle filter* performed using Lee filter and a kernel size of 5×5 pixels. *Terrain flattening* step is based on the algorithm given in [Small \(2011\)](#), with parameters SRTM 3 s and a bilinear interpolation set for digital elevation model (DEM) and DEM resampling method, respectively. This resampling method is chosen based on [Truckenbrodt et al. \(2019\)](#) who suggested it as the best compromise between quality of topographic normalization and processing time consumption. Similarly, to terrain flattening, *terrain correction* utilized the same parameters for DEM, but also some additional parameters. Namely, bilinear interpolation was chosen for an image resampling method, 10 m as a pixel spacing, and *alignToStandardGrid* was set to *True* in order to have all the processed Sentinel-1 dates aligned. Presented processing workflow outputs bands for VV and VH polarizations as Gamma0 backscatter (radar cross-section with respect to local incidence angle given by DEM). Some authors already discussed superiority of Gamma0 over Sigma0 ([Small, 2011](#); [Wicks et al., 2018](#)). Resulting products were saved in geotiff format and included these two bands, while their ratio ($SR = \frac{VH}{VV}$) was added later. All three served as features in the analysis afterwards.

3. Methodology

Methodology framework is depicted in [Fig. 5](#). Three algorithms are selected for evaluation, namely Random Forest, Convolutional Neural

Network and Transformer. Random Forest (RF) is a classical representative of machine learning group of algorithms. It is a bagging (bootstrap aggregation) ensemble learning method made up from collection of decision trees that create forest. Every decision tree is trained using bootstrapped dataset and gives a single vote for the class output of the input sample. The class label with the most votes across the ensemble wins ([Breiman, 2001](#)). Convolutional neural network (CNN) is a well-known deep learning architecture used to solve various pattern recognition tasks. Over the last two decades, regarding the extreme increase in annotated datasets availability, as well as manufacturing improvements of graphics processor units, a tremendous progress of CNNs algorithms has been made thus achieving outstanding results on various tasks ([Gu et al., 2018](#)). Transformers (TR) are considered nowadays as the state-of-the-art in the deep learning community. Self-attention Transformer models ([Vaswani et al., 2017](#)) represent a type of neural network initially designed as encoder–decoder models for sequence-to-sequence tasks like language translation. These models employ attention mechanisms to extract features from specific time steps in an input time series signal. In the context of the crop classification task, the word embedding step is omitted. This decision is based on the continuous spatial nature of the satellite time series data. Instead, positional encoding is introduced into the time series signal. This addition is crucial because self-attention cannot inherently leverage the sequential correlation present in time series data ([Rußwurm and Körner, 2020](#)).

For each algorithm four different model approaches were analyzed, given in [Table 2](#). Each differ in data in use, phases and knowledge taken from historical model. **Naive** represents a case where model was trained on historical data and applied as such on test data. **Transfer**

Table 2

Characteristics of different models. Phase A relies on source domain data, phase B relies on a part of target domain data, and the testing phase relies on the remaining part of target domain data.

Model	CNN _{naive} /RF _{naive} /TR _{naive}	CNN _{TL} /RF _{TL} /TR _{TL}	CNN _{FS (hist)} /RF _{FS (hist)} /TR _{FS (hist)}	CNN _{FS (2021)} /RF _{FS (2021)} /TR _{FS (2021)}
Approach	Naive transfer	Transfer learning	From scratch (historical)	From scratch (2021)
Data used	Historical	Historical & 2021	Historical & 2021	2021
Phases				
A	1. Hypp. optim. (loyo) 2. Model training	1. Hypp. optim. (loyo) 2. Model training	1. Hypp. optim. (loyo)	<i>none</i>
B	<i>none</i>	1. Retraining	1. Training	1. Hypp. optim. 2. Training
Testing			✓	
Used knowledge from historical model	Hyperparameters, weights (original)	Hyperparameters, weights (updated)	Hyperparameters	<i>none</i>

Learning approach is approach where model trained on historical data is retrained using small portion of target domain training data and applied to test data. **From scratch (historical)** is a model that used historical data only to optimize hyperparameters, but used portion of target domain training data to train a model. Lastly, **From scratch (2021)** used only target domain training data both for hyperparameter optimization and model training (does not use historical data).

Source domain data, i.e., 2017–2020 season, was used for hyperparameter optimization and model training for models CNN_{naive}, RF_{naive}, TR_{naive}, CNN_{TL}, RF_{TL} and TR_{TL}, utilizing leave-one-year-out (*loyo*) approach (described in Section 3.2), while for models CNN_{FS (hist)}, RF_{FS (hist)} and TR_{FS (hist)} was used just for hyperparameter optimization.

Target domain data, i.e., 2021 season, was split into three stratified sets: training (30%), validation (10%) and test set (60%). If a parcel was chosen for a particular set during the data split (which also applies for source domain split during *loyo*), then all of the associated pixels were put in the same set, thereby safeguarding the method against data leakage. Training set is smaller than usually seen in literature because the background idea is to try to rely on historical data (i.e. source domain) and use as little as possible the data coming from the target domain. This training data is used for training in CNN_{FS (hist)}, RF_{FS (hist)} and TR_{FS (hist)} models, retraining in CNN_{TL}, RF_{TL} and TR_{TL} models, and hyperparameter optimization and training in CNN_{FS (2021)}, RF_{FS (2021)} and TR_{FS (2021)} models (Fig. 5, Table 2). All respective re/training and hyperparameter optimization is done at 5% interval. Validation set was used only for hyperparameter optimization in CNN_{FS (2021)}, RF_{FS (2021)} and TR_{FS (2021)} models. The test set was identical for all 12 models.

3.1. Kolmogorov–Smirnov goodness-of-fit test for two domains

Before running ML and DL models, it was necessary to check if the two domains (source and target) are different. Generally speaking, seasonal differences mainly originate from management- and weather-induced variabilities which were, in this case, only considered in terms of their impact on radar backscatter and related derivatives, not as an explicit feature (predictor). In this experiment source domain is defined jointly by season 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 data (often regarded as historical data), while 2021 season data is taken for target domain since that is the year we want to transfer the model to.

Following the work by Yang et al. (2020), in order to consider source and target domains defined by feature space X and marginal probability distribution $P(X)$ to be different (which is one of prerequisites for transfer learning), it is necessary that either their feature spaces are different ($X_s \neq X_t$) or that their marginal probability distributions are different ($P(X_s) \neq P(X_t)$). In this particular case feature spaces are the same, and the identity of the two marginal probability distributions was tested using Kolmogorov–Smirnov two-sided test, by comparing respective samples (e.i., pairs of features) of the two domains. Kolmogorov–Smirnov test is a nonparametric goodness-of-fit test that compares two independent samples on joint underlying

Table 3

Grid search for hyperparameter optimization.

Algorithm	Hyperparameter	Values
RF	n_estimators	[100, 500, 1000]
	max_depth	[1, 5, 10, 50]
	min_samples_leaf	[1, 5, 10, 50, 100]
CNN	n_conv_blocks	[2, 3, 4]
	n_filters	[4, 8, 16, 32]
	kernel_size	[4, 8, 16, 32]
	dropout	[0.25, 0.50, 0.75]
TR	d_model	[32, 64, 128, 256]
	n_head	[1, 2]
	n_layers	[4, 5, 6]
	d_inner	[64, 128, 256]
	dropout	[0, 0.25]

distribution (Kottegoda and Rosso, 2008). Test statistics is calculated as:

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{mn}{m+n}} \cdot D_{m,n} \quad (1)$$

where

$$D_{m,n} = \sup_x |F_m(x) - G_n(x)| \quad (2)$$

and F_m and G_n represent two empirical distribution functions of the two samples of size m and n , respectively, and \sup is for the supremum function. The null hypothesis states that both samples have the same underlying distribution and it is rejected if the p -value of the test is less than the level of significance which was set for all tests to 0.05

3.2. Hyperparameter optimization

Although some studies neglect the process of hyperparameter tuning by referring to conclusions previously drawn in literature on rather small improvements achieved (Pelletier et al., 2017), this study decisively runs this operation in order to find the optimal parameter settings. Grid search method was used for this task.

In case of RF, parameters to tune were the number of trees in the forest ($n_{estimators}$), maximum depth of the tree (max_depth) and the minimum number of samples in the leaf ($min_samples_leaf$; Table 3). RF is rarely prone to the overfitting issue due to the large number of decision trees produced by randomly selecting a subset of training samples and a subset of variables for splitting at each tree node (Belgiu and Drăguț, 2016).

On the other hand, the basic CNN architecture which consists of two logical blocks, convolutional base and classifier, is used within this analysis as one of the deep learning classification tool representatives (Fig. 6). The convolutional base consists of multiple convolutional blocks and serves as a feature extractor used to obtain generic patterns from the input signal useful for crop classification. Each convolutional block comprised convolutional, Dropout (Srivastava et al., 2014),

Fig. 6. General form of CNN-1D architecture in the experiment. Tested models vary in number of convolutional blocks, number of filters, kernel size and dropout value.

Fig. 7. Transformer network architecture in the experiment.

BatchNorm (Ioffe and Szegedy, 2015) and ReLU (Nair and Hinton, 2010) layers, respectively. Note that within the last convolutional layer, the kernel size is set to 1, which produces a consistent number of feature maps regardless of the number of convolutional filters in the previous block. Finally, an Adaptive Average Pooling layer is used to

aggregate features produced by individual convolutional filters and create a consistent output size for cases where the input length varies. This model property allows to explore the impact of different input sizes due to the early-season mapping or number of valid acquisitions used for data generation. Finally, the classifier consists of a single fully connected layer followed by Softmax layer to produce the classified output. In order to optimize CNN architecture different number of convolutional blocks (n_{conv_blocks}), number of filters ($n_{filters}$), kernel sizes ($kernel_size$) and dropout ($dropout$) values were thoroughly explored. Sets of values evaluated for each hyperparameter can be seen in Table 3. The early stopping criteria based on the validation loss is used during the model training in order to fight the model overfitting towards training samples (Prechelt, 2002).

Following the work by Rußwurm et al. (2019), the Transformer network initiates with the step of positional encoding (Fig. 7). After this, the time series data is converted into feature representations of higher dimensions using one or more Transformer blocks. In each block, features are encoded using a multihead self-attention mechanism, and this is followed by several dense layers that operate independently on each time instance. To improve the flow of information and gradients through the network, skip connections are implemented between layers. Additionally, layer normalization is employed consistently across the model. The output of the final layer is then reduced by a global maximum pooling through time dimension. This reduced representation is then mapped to class scores through a final fully connected layer with a softmax activation function. Following hyperparameters were optimized for Transformer architecture: the dimensionality of the hidden states (d_{model}), number of layers in the Transformer encoder (n_{layers}), number of heads in the multi-head attention mechanism (n_{head}), dropout probability ($dropout$) and dimensionality of the inner layer of the feed-forward networks (d_{inner}) (Table 3).

Hyperparameter optimization process for models CNN_{naive} , CNN_{TL} , $CNN_{FS(hist)}$, RF_{naive} , RF_{TL} , $RF_{FS(hist)}$, TR_{naive} , TR_{TL} and $TR_{FS(hist)}$ was done using historical data and leave-one-year-out technique. This means that input data referring to years 2017–2020 was used in such a way that 4-fold cross-validation was performed, so that each year-data represented only once a validation dataset. This approach

imitates our general idea where characteristics of the target year data are unknown in advance, thus assuming better generalization than simple train-test split approach. Once done, the average result per hyperparameter combination was extracted. Metrics used were F1 score and time complexity. F1 score is taking the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall as presented in Eq. (3):

$$F1 \text{ score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN}$$

with TP, FP and FN respectively denoting True Positives, False Positives, and False Negatives, while time complexity refers to the time spent to fit the model. Features (acquisitions dates) used for this purpose ranged from the beginning of March until the end of September since this period is characterized with typical phenological developments for all crop types considered. Hyperparameter optimization process for models $CNN_{FS(2021)}$, $RF_{FS(2021)}$ and $TR_{FS(2021)}$ was already discussed, holding analogous choice of features.

Once these results were obtained, the Pareto front was drawn to perform the final choice of hyperparameters. Pareto front is a concept in multi-objective optimization based on non-dominating solutions. In this particular case, this means that no other solution (point), rather than those creating “the front”, is giving better results on both axes (F1 score and time complexity). In other words, if we were to increase F1 score, then time complexity would be compromised, and vice versa. Of the points that construct Pareto front, a single point (solution) was selected using *kneed* Python library that enables finding a point of the line with maximum curvature (Satopaa et al., 2011). This point marks the chosen hyperparameters setting.

3.3. Model choice and transfer learning

In addition to previous, a choice of a model (denoted as *historical model* throughout the paper) was done by taking a step back and looking at the four corresponding folds for the chosen hyperparameter combination. The one with the highest F1 score was selected and forwarded to phase B and testing.

In Transfer Learning approach, historical model was retrained using portion of 2021 season training data. Retraining was carried out in increments of 5% of the data, until reaching the previously allocated 30% for re/training. Each of these increments went through five iterations. Simultaneously, testing was conducted using previously reserved 60% of the target domain data for evaluation. The increment of 5% was chosen in order to investigate the impact of varying volumes of data on performance of Transfer Learning.

In the scope of RF, boosting knowledge of the source domain trained model can be done by increasing the number of trees while adding target domain samples and fitting new trees over limited target domain samples. Decision trees of the forest previously built solely on source domain samples remain unchanged, only extra trees are added to the forest to extract additional knowledge from target domain.

In the scope of CNN, transfer learning is done by using the representations learned by a pre-trained model to extract interesting features from target domain samples. Namely, a set of layers from the convolutional base is frozen, which prevents their weights from being updated during training. That way previously learned features using the source domain (which comprise higher amounts of information compared to the target domain) are not modified and useful knowledge could be reused for the target domain. The reason is that the representations learned by the convolutional base are likely to extract certain generic concepts within the input signal useful when the number of samples within the target domain is limited. On the other hand, fully connected layer (classifier) representations acquired during the model training, tend to be more specific regarding the source domain. For that reason, fully connected layer weights were updated using the information provided within the target domain.

Similarly to transfer learning process executed utilizing convolutional neural networks, a set of weights within the TransferEncoder layer was frozen, while only the weights from the final fully connected layer were updated during model training. This approach allowed a pre-trained model to extract the general features learned from information present in the source domain, whereas parameters in classifier part are specifically adjusted towards the target domain dataset.

4. Results

4.1. Domain difference

The first insight into data is given in Fig. 8 that displays averaged time series of the two domains per respective set of features, namely VH, VV and SR. Despite nested pitfalls, due to e.g. aggregation of different classes, the graphs still nicely illustrate similar trends in domains together with their substantial differences. Differences may originate from specific distribution of classes between agricultural seasons (although they are quite related), distinct weather characteristics and altered management practice. To statistically verify that these differences meet criteria of TL for the experiment, Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests were performed for all pairs of features between two domains. For all tests, calculated *p*-value was smaller than the set threshold of $\frac{0.05}{K}$ where *K* equals number of tests, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis that the two samples are coming from the same distribution for all 105 tests. For this reason, two domains of interest can safely be considered different.

4.2. Hyperparameter optimization

With the setup described in Section 3.2 there were 60 combinations of parameters examined for RF and 144 combinations examined for CNN and TR each. In *loyo* approach each combination was assessed four times, and their averaged performances per parameter settings are given in Fig. 9.

For models $CNN_{FS(2021)}$, $RF_{FS(2021)}$ and $TR_{FS(2021)}$ hyperparameter optimization was done 18 times (6 times per each algorithm due to chosen 5% increments in training data, i.e., 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% and 30%), in a single fold with 5 iterations.

The non-dominated solutions, shown by a star marker, are creating the Pareto front (green line). The intersection of the black dashed vertical line and the Pareto front is the knee point, a trade-off between model performance and complexity, that represents the selected solution, i.e., combination of hyperparameters. For the cases shown in Fig. 9 that relate to historical models, optimal hyperparameter setting is [100, 50, 50] respectively for [*n_estimators*, *max_depth*, *min_samples_leaf*] for RF algorithm, [3, 8, 32, 0.25] respectively for [*n_conv_blocks*, *n_filters*, *kernel_size*, *dropout*] for CNN algorithm, and [256, 2, 4, 256, 0] respectively for [*d_model*, *n_head*, *n_layers*, *d_inner*, *dropout*] TR algorithm.

4.3. Test dataset

Performance of various models on test dataset is shown in Fig. 10. CNN models are given in solid lines, RF in dashed lines and TR in dotted lines. Each color represents different scenario. Since re/training was done at 5% data increments, the evaluation is presented in the same way.

CNN_{naive} , shown in blue, achieves an F1 score of 78%. This indicates that it performs quite descent for a given task. TR_{naive} performs 2% lower, i.e. reaches F1 score of 76%. Meanwhile, RF_{naive} lags behind, with an F1 score of 73%. It is the least effective among all the models we have tested. Since all of these three scenarios are essentially just pre-trained models applied directly to our target domain test dataset, their performance is a constant in Fig. 10.

When speaking about TL approach, represented by orange lines on our chart, CNN_{TL} exhibits a consistently high F1 score ranging between

Fig. 8. Averaged time series for VH (top), VV (middle) and SR (bottom) sets of features for source domain (2017–2020 seasons) and target domain (2021 season), with x-axis representing image acquisition dates and y-axis representing radar backscatter value.

84% and 87%. This impressive range firmly positions CNN_{TL} among the top-performing models in our analysis. It demonstrates a remarkable capability to deliver robust results across different scenarios. In contrast, RF_{TL} achieves an F1 score between 80% and 84%. This places it in a solid middle ground in terms of performance when compared to the other models under consideration. While not reaching the same heights as CNN_{TL} , RF_{TL} maintains a respectable level of performance across various conditions. Similarly to RF_{TL} , F1 score for TR_{TL} ranges between 81% and 84% for different data increments.

Also, at the onset of our evaluation, all three models $CNN_{FS}^{(hist)}$, $RF_{FS}^{(hist)}$ and $TR_{FS}^{(hist)}$, exhibited a commendable F1 score, beginning at approximately 80% (at a 5% increment). However, as we progressed in our analysis, $CNN_{FS}^{(hist)}$ demonstrated a modest rise, reaching a peak of nearly 85% F1 score. In contrast, $RF_{FS}^{(hist)}$ and

$TR_{FS}^{(hist)}$ surpassed expectations by achieving F1 scores exceeding 87%. While $TR_{FS}^{(hist)}$ exhibited steady increase throughout, $RF_{FS}^{(hist)}$ faced performance drop at 10% data increment.

Finally, F1 score fluctuated within the range of 77% to 82% for $CNN_{FS}^{(2021)}$ model. On the other hand, $RF_{FS}^{(2021)}$ showcased a more impressive performance range, spanning from 77% to an outstanding 88% F1 score when more training data is being available. What is particularly noteworthy is that $RF_{FS}^{(2021)}$ attained the highest F1 score among all the models we examined, emphasizing its exceptional performance in the task at hand. F1 score of $TR_{FS}^{(2021)}$ model steadily increased from 80% to 88%, making its performances at each increment nearly identical to those of $TR_{FS}^{(hist)}$ model.

Confusion matrices for CNN_{TL} at 5% increment and $RF_{FS}^{(2021)}$ at 30% increment are given in Fig. 11. The first one is chosen since

Fig. 9. Results of RF (top), CNN (middle) and TR (bottom) hyperparameter optimization on source domain, averaged per parameter setting (on 4-folds). Stars represent non-dominated solutions that create the Pareto front (green line). The intersection of the black dashed line and the Pareto front is the knee point that was chosen as the final hyperparameter setting.

it represents the best performing model in scenario where the least target domain data was used, while the second is chosen because it is the best performing model overall. It can be seen that they quite resemble to one another, and that none is ultimately better on all classes. Good discriminatory is found for corn, wheat, soybean, sugar beat, barley and oilseed rape (90% or more, with single exception of 89% for barley in the first case). A bit lower is found for sunflower (80% and 81%), followed by clover (75% and 71%) and orchard with only 59%. The subpar discriminatory performance observed for clover and orchard is likely attributed to their underrepresentation in the dataset, as they each constitute only 2% of the total number of samples

(Fig. 3). In such cases, characterized by imbalanced data, Precision and Recall metrics represent useful indicators of classification performance. Former indicates the likelihood of classifier prediction as being correct, whereas latter gives an indication that the classifier is successful at identifying instances from the class of interest. In other words, Precision focuses on reducing false positives, whereas Recall concentrates on minimizing false negatives. For that reason, both metrics are estimated per class in Table 4 for the two selected models. Based on values provided within the table, it can be seen that CNN model gives a good trade-off between Precision and Recall for all classes. On the other hand, in case of clovers, sunflowers and orchards, RF misclassified a

Fig. 10. Results of various approaches of CNN, RF and TR algorithms on test dataset; **naive** - pure application of pre-trained model, **TL** - transfer learning, **FS (hist)** - modeling from scratch using only pre-trained model's hyperparameters, **FS (2021)** - modeling from scratch without any prior knowledge (traditional approach).

Fig. 11. Normalized confusion matrices for two scenarios: CNN_{TL} at 5% increment (left) and RF_{FS(2021)} at 30% increment (right).

high ratio of instances as different classes, which can also be seen in Fig. 11 where orchard are often misclassified as corn (22%), sunflower as soybean (13%) or corn (6%) and finally clover as corn (15%). Given that corn is the predominant crop type in the dataset, it appears that

both models are inclined to classify ambiguous predictions as corn, relying prevalently on statistical likelihood. However, based on the results provided within Table 4 and Fig. 11, CNN model shows higher generalization capabilities compared to RF.

Table 4
Precision and Recall of CNN_{TL} at 5% increment and RF_{FS (2021)} at 30% given per class.

Model	Metric	Corn	Wheat	Soybean	Sugar beat	Barley	Clover	Sunflower	Oilseed rape	Orchard
CNN _{TL} at 5% increment	Precision	0.92	0.96	0.85	0.92	0.78	0.69	0.89	0.98	0.56
	Recall	0.91	0.93	0.90	0.92	0.89	0.74	0.80	0.96	0.59
RF _{FS (2021)} at 30% increment	Precision	0.88	0.93	0.80	0.97	0.81	0.85	0.93	0.99	0.95
	Recall	0.95	0.96	0.90	0.86	0.80	0.28	0.63	0.96	0.35

5. Discussion

One way to deal with crop classification in areas of limited training data is to train a model in another region/year and transfer to the target one (Hao et al., 2020). This study aimed to investigate if SAR-based crop classification models can be transferred in time and explore their applicability. The research showed that it is indeed possible to transfer knowledge of crop classification model in temporal domain within a single agricultural region, despite being as large as 21,500 km². Although simple transfer of model can yield good results, adapting the model using in-situ data can boost its performance furthermore. In general, the more in-situ data is added to training set, the better classification results are achieved.

Crop mapping can benefit from historical data-based model if in-situ data for target year is very scarce or unavailable. However, when certain portion of this data is met (e.g. 15% increment in our case or ca. 360 parcels), traditional crop mapping approaches could be more suitable and even outperform transfer learning approaches. Still, while existing model would require only retraining, building new model from scratch in traditional way would require hyperparameter optimization prior to model training which can take substantial amount of time.

This study generally addressed limited availability of target domain data, despite taking different increments of in-situ data into account throughout experimentation. Regarding traditional mapping approaches, it resulted in agreement with previous findings on ensemble learning models being better than neural networks (Yuan and Lin, 2020), when small portion of data is available for training.

Unless the crop classification study is trying to replicate an existing one, which is not the present case, systematically assessing and comparing crop classification studies presents difficulties due to the inherent differences not only in the quality of the training and testing datasets (Antonijević et al., 2023), but also in quantity of data, experiment designs including choice of crops, time and locations, chosen evaluation metrics and other relevant parameters (Rusňák et al., 2023). For this reason, it was rather challenging to compare with other crop mapping studies.

In Arias et al. (2018), authors achieved the highest overall accuracy of 79% utilizing Sentinel-1 temporal signatures for 11 crop types on rather imbalanced training set with 400 parcels. The closest analogy to our experiment would correspond to approximately 15% increment in e.g. RF_{FS (2021)}, i.e. F1 score of about 86%.

Specifically speaking of model transferring, Hu et al. (2022) reported OA of 89% when transferring model from 2019 to 2020 season using naive approach. Potential respective pair from this study could be the worst performing model RF_{naive} with only 73% F1 score. However, their study classified only 4 crop types in comparison to our 9 crop types which is a more complex task by itself. They also used combination of SAR with optical sensor that, although beneficial, could likely be obstructed from use due to weather dependency. Their findings showed that the combination of sensors reached about 1% higher OA than the Sentinel-2 only scenario, but did not investigate the radar only scenario. Temporal transfer learning in combination with spatial transfer was tested by Hao et al. (2020) that reported impressive results (OA of 98%, 86% and 95%), using combination of optical sensors only (harmonized Landsat -8 and Sentinel-2 data), yet only 2 or 3 crop types per testing region were assessed. Both studies relied on RF algorithm and considered imbalanced datasets for which F1 score metric may be more relevant than OA. On the other hand, You and Dong (2020)

explored all three scenarios (optical only, radar only, and combination of sensors) in their research. A naive transferring approach using only Sentinel-1 achieved poor results, i.e., F1 score of just 67% and 58% for corn and soybean, respectively. However, using only Sentinel-2 imagery they managed to reach an F1 score of over 90% for both crops. Combination of the two sensors yielded 0.3% higher F1 score for corn, while F1 score for soybean was 0.2% lower than using Sentinel-2 only.

Relying only on optical sensor, i.e., Sentinel-2, authors in Wang et al. (2023) reported F1 score between 84% and 92% with their proposed deep adaptation crop classification network (DACCN) when transferring models between subsequent seasons in the same region. Again, only corn and soybean were classified, while all the other crop types were classified as “other”. Račič et al. (2024) performed multi-year early crop mapping using Sentinel-2 and achieved an average F1 score of 82.5%, without any reference data from the target year (respective pair from our study could be CNN_{naive} with F1 score of 78%). They were able to exceed this performance using in season ground truth by 210th DOY with 48,000 (9% of available dataset) samples from the target year. Authors in Rusňák et al. (2023) reported mean accuracy ranging between 88% and 92% for temporal transferability scenario. Cai et al. (2018) investigated in-season mapping using Landsat data, and reported 95% classification accuracy by the end of June when applying pretrained models to a target years. They utilized 13- and 14-years long time-series in this research and classified corn and soybean.

Transferring only model architecture without transferring model weights, such as e.g. CNN_{FS (hist)}, gave promising results in our test case, which is different from remarks given in Jo et al. (2022), who tested transfer learning for single crop type but in different regions.

Conclusions from Gadiraju and Vatsavai (2020), on superiority of strategies that include fine-tuning of pre-trained models over strategies such as naive transfer are also confirmed in our case. However, their superiority over models trained from scratch should be taken with precautions since it was not indisputably proven within our experiment.

Finally, to rest assure that created models truly generalize well without overfitting, one can compare Figs. 9 and 10. By analyzing these graphs, it can be seen that the best performing model, for all three algorithms RF, CNN and TR, is not exceeding 75% of F1 score during hyperparameter optimization process (Fig. 9). On the other hand, the same models evaluated on the independent test set (Fig. 10) do not show any decrease in classification performance compared to source-domain validation performance. What is more, corresponding models have shown comparably higher performance evaluated on the target domain, which proves that trained models optimized in the source domain are highly generalized and perform successfully on an independent dataset.

6. Conclusion

Using highly dense time series of Sentinel-1 imagery, this paper analyzed various strategies for transferring crop mapping models over time, contrasting them with the traditional, non-transferring approach. It examined three algorithms, namely Random Forest, Convolutional Neural Networks and Transformer. Nine different crop types were classified in the experiment which are typically grown in Southeastern Europe, i.e., corn, wheat, soybean, sugar beat, barley, clover, sunflower, oilseed rape and orchard. All together, 12 different scenarios were tested of which RF_{naive} performed the worst, while CNN_{TL} and

RF_{FS (2021)} were the two best performing models at different increments of re/training data. This means that pre-trained RF model on historical data and applied to new season data as such did not yield high performance. On the other hand, combination of CNN with Transfer Learning achieved promising results when little target domain data is available (less than 360 parcels in this case), surpassed later by the traditional crop mapping approach as more parcels were available.

Results showed that the model can detect oilseed rape and wheat with highest reliability while orchard and clover are the two crop types most difficult to classify, presumably due to underrepresentation in the dataset which may have prevented the model from learning relevant feature representation and obtaining generic patterns for crop classification for the two labels.

In our study, we emphasize the importance of accuracy as a key metric in evaluating crop classification model's performance, balancing it with the consideration of time complexity. Though this turned out to be of high importance for Vojvodina case, it could however become vital for large-scale applications such as regional or continental map updates. The study's secondary finding reveals that beyond a certain accuracy level, any further model improvement could become marginal relative to the additional time required.

While temporal transfer learning exhibited significant capability, the experiment also highlighted that its application should not be unconditionally adopted as it faced a direct challenge from the traditional crop mapping approach when a certain portion of target domain data was available. Still, traditional approach requires hyperparameter optimization prior to model training, while transfer learning requires only model retraining which may make substantial difference in processing time.

From the practical standpoint of agricultural management, the paper's findings significantly reduce labor costs by minimizing the need for extensive field trips and personnel for ground truth data collection. With these methods, a handful of trips can replace 20 full-day field trips with 40 people (referring to our study), providing an efficient overview of seasonal crop distribution. This streamlined approach still offers objective information vital for informed decision-making. Also, in situations where detailed data collection is impossible, such as natural disasters or war conflicts, transfer learning ensures the continuity of crop mapping with minimal resources and manpower. This not only cuts down time and effort but also reduces potential errors, as training and monitoring a smaller team is more manageable.

This work concludes with several open questions that merit further exploration. The first one deals with searching for a better temporal transfer learning approach that could potentially outperform traditional mapping in all circumstances. Different number of frozen layers should be explored for this purpose in the first place. Alternatively, even though SAR data proved to be a reliable data source for TL tasks, further improvements in performances can be expected when radar data is combined with other data sources such as optical multispectral or weather data. Integrating SAR with optical data would help to better understand specific sensor data limitations, while weather data would explicitly address seasonal specificities that radar backscatter could not. Further experiments could be dedicated to analyzing TL in spatial domain where source and target domains will not represent the same area. It would be also interesting to investigate how much TL could help when tasks in two domains are not the same, i.e., classify different crop types in source and target domain. Finally, different ML and DL algorithms should also be explored, as well as early-season crop mapping.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Miloš Pandžić: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dejan Pavlović:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Predrag Matavulj:**

Conceptualization. **Sanja Brdar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Oskar Marko:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Vladimir Crnojević:** Funding acquisition. **Milan Kilibarda:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Code is made publicly available at https://github.com/pandzaa/TempTL_S1 Parts of data may be shared after assessment of individual requests.

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